

Research Paper

Structure-Based Virtual Screening and Molecular Dynamics Simulation for
Identifying Potential Therapeutics against Herpes Simplex Encephalitis

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ABSTRACT

Essentially regarded as HSV-1 caused, Herpes Simplex Encephalitis is an acute and lethal form of neuroinfections with scarcely any options for treatment. Here, we have applied structure-based virtual screening and molecular dynamics (MD) simulations in an effort to find potential inhibitors targeting the viral thymidine kinase mutant Y101F (PDB ID: 1E2L), a crucial enzyme in the replication of HSV. A library of FDA-approved drugs was screened against the active site of 1E2L, and five drugs showing good binding affinity and beneficial interactions with important residues have been chosen: Dutasteride, Paritaprevir, Pimozide, Lumacaftor, and Tucatinib. Next, MD and Normal Mode Analysis (NMA) offered complementary mechanistic insights into the varying degrees of structural flexibility, conformational dynamics, and possible allosteric regulation of 1E2L. Shape and B-factor comparison highlighted flexible regions for the binding, while eigenvalue and variance analyses stressed the importance of low-frequency modes in the motion of molecules. Covariance mapping yielded correlated or anti-correlated movements within the residues integral to allosteric interactions, while the Elastic Network Model (ENM) was employed to reveal rigid and flexible regions that drive functional dynamics. Taken together, these findings point toward the selected compounds being reasonable candidates for repurposing as anti-HSV therapeutics via inhibition of the viral kinase. The combined method involving virtual screening and MD simulations is set up as a framework for rational drug development against HSE.

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1. Introduction

Herpes Simplex Encephalitis (HSE) has been cited as a rarely occurring, possibly even deadly disease of the viral infection of the central nervous system, mostly due to the Herpes Simplex Virus type 1 (HSV-1) [1]. This kind of condition often inflicts serious neurological damage and comes with a mortality rate that multiplies if not treated [2]. Even though many antiviral therapies, like acyclovir, are there, resistance and treatment failure are major areas of concern that call for the discovery of new therapeutic strategies [3].

HSV-1 thymidine kinase, or TK, is an essential enzyme that plays a critical role in viral DNA replication through nucleoside analog phosphorylation. Antiviral drugs primarily target this enzyme, as it is crucial for viral replication [4]. Mutations in the thymidine kinase gene can result in resistance to traditional antiviral agents, and this presents a very real and serious challenge for HSE treatment [5]. Among these mutations, the Y101F mutant has emerged as an important variant that changes the enzyme's binding affinity and catalytic activity, thereby conferring drug resistance [6].

The clinical challenges posed by Y101F HSV-1 TK mutant present a promising target for structure-based drug design [7].

Computational strategies like receptor-based virtual screening enable identification of a possible lead from the existing FDA-approved drug libraries, thus fast track the process of drug repurposing [8]. The study goal would harness advanced molecular docking and simulation techniques to identify promising candidates that could satisfactorily bind to the Y101F mutant for potential new therapeutic approaches for the management of HSE [9].

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Protein Structure Preparation

The Y101F mutation of the Herpes Simplex Virus type 1 thymidine kinase crystal structure (PDB ID: 1E2L) was derived from the RCSB Protein Data Bank [10]. This PDB file was refined by PDB-REDO such as to develop structure quality and hence facilitate accurate molecular modeling [11]. PDB-REDO is a highly effective tool for enhancing geometric models in crystallography, typically through optimization of geometry, repositioning of atoms, improving electron density fitting and removing such defects as missed atom parts and/or crystal artifacts. Overall validation by SAVES v6.0 took an improved structure through thorough scrutinization [12]. The

latter includes assessments through PROSA, in which overall model quality is estimated through z-score calculations and comparison of scores against similar-sized experimentally determined structures. This refined structure hence yielded a favorable z-score within the range typical for native proteins, confirming its suitability for subsequent computation analyses [13].

2.2 Virtual Screening Using DrugRep

In the search for candidates capable of being used therapeutically against herpes simplex encephalitis (HSE) potential therapeutic candidates for HSE were identified through receptor-based virtual screening on the established computational platform "DrugRep" [14]. DrugRep indicates a rapid screening of any FDA approved compound library against the specific target protein in the form of hypothetical inhibitors or modulators [15]. The DrugRep server is designed to conduct *in silico* virtual screening and predict possible hits among the library of compounds able to interact with the receptor [16].

Graft new Y101F mutant of HSV-1 thymidine kinase (PDB ID: 1E2L) refined-and-validated structure in Drug-Rep as a receptor model. The procedure of screening consisted of the following series:

Protein preparation: Protonation states were set, hydrogen atoms added, and force field parameters assigned to refine PDB files for docking [17]. Ligand Library Selection: The screening was performed on the entire library of FDA-approved drugs to guarantee that any candidate selected thereafter had an already established safety profile [18]. Molecular Docking: Docking simulations of receptor-ligand complexes were performed by DrugRep to predict binding affinities considering complementarity interactions between the compounds and receptor active site [19]. Scoring and Ranking: Structures were evaluated with a scoring algorithm based on factors such as binding free energy, hydrogen bonding, hydrophobic interactions, and molecular fit within the active site [20]. The top 100 compounds with the highest binding affinity scores based on these criteria were selected for further examination [21]. These high-ranking compounds proved worthy of further forensic examination from the perspective of molecular dynamics simulations and interaction studies due to their interesting potential in interaction with the Y101F mutant.

2.3 Protein-Ligand Interaction Analysis

To delve into the molecular interactions between the identified top-scoring

compounds and the Y101F mutant of HSV-1 thymidine kinase, an analysis of protein-ligand interactions was performed using BIOVIA Discovery Studio [22]. This software is a complete suite of tools for visualizing and analyzing molecular interactions three-dimensionally [23].

The key parameters considered during the analysis were: Hydrogen Bond: Recognition of significant hydrogen bonds contributing to ligand stability and specificity in the active site [24]; Hydrophobic interaction: Mapping of hydrophobic contacts to understand non-polar interactions that enhance ligand binding; Pi-Pi stacking and Electrostatic interaction: Examination of aromatic stacking and ionic interactions solidifying ligand-receptor affinity [25]. This extensive interaction analysis assisted in determining the structural features responsible for the strong binding affinity of the shortlisted compounds and further guided their selection for validation by molecular dynamics simulations [26].

2.4 Molecular Dynamics Simulation

In order to study the stability and dynamic behavior of protein-ligand complexes, an iMODS based molecular dynamics simulation is being carried out [27]. iMODS is a comprehensive web-based tool offering

some important dynamics analysis that estimate molecular flexibility and structural stability [28].

The highlights of the analysis done in iMODS included: Molecular Deformability: it assesses flexible regions in protein structure and tries to predict conformational changes potential [29]. B-Factors (Atomic Displacement Parameters): analysis of structural states by the fluctuations in atomic movement gives a clue about the atomic regions being prone to degenerating or flexible states [30]. Eigenvalues: eigenvalues are quantified and expressed in terms of energy required for the molecular deformation; lower eigenvalues indicate easier motion and, hence, a greater degree of flexibility [31]. Variance Analysis: indicate the individual and cumulative measure of variance that cuts off dynamic motions significantly under the protein structure [32]. Covariance Map: Map the correlated atomic motion to develop an understanding of cooperative molecular behavior [33]. Elastic Network Model (E.N.M): Provide the elastic network to visualize critical motion pathways and identify regions significantly structural in nature [34]. These important analyses throw some light stability, flexibility as well as dynamic behavior of the protein-ligand complexes being studied, ensuring that the

shortlisted compounds maintain good interaction under simulated biological conditions [35].

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Protein Structure Validation

3.1.1. PDB REDO

Figure 1: Kleywegt-like Plot Depicting Conformational Dynamics of the Y101F Mutant of HSV-1 Thymidine Kinase during Molecular Dynamics Simulation

Y101F mutant of Herpes Simplex Virus type 1 thymidine kinase Kleywegt-like plot substantially reveals certain crucial insights into the protein conformational dynamics that run off during molecular dynamics simulations. Such clustering of favorable ϕ and ψ angles, particularly in regions of β -sheet and α -helix conformations, suggests that in terms of overall structural stability, the Y101F mutation does not diverge widely

from the native enzyme. Scattered points and connecting lines indicate local flexibility and transitions that might be important for crucial functional sites. Such transitions may interfere with either substrate-binding or inhibitor- and drug-binding, indicating the need for extended analysis such as RMSD, RMSF, and hydrogen bonding studies for a greater understanding of the mutation effects

on the enzyme catalytic behavior and its implications for antiviral drug design.

Figure 2: Comparison of Model Quality Metrics for the Y101F Mutant of HSV-1 Thymidine Kinase Before and After PDB-REDO Refinement

The analysis of model quality with respect to the Y101F mutant of Herpes Simplex Virus type 1 thymidine kinase shows that, with reference to the model accuracies being better and the overfitting being less, the R-Free values are lowered following PDB-REDO refinement, implying better structural integrity. An improved Ramachandran Plot Z-score indicates better backbone geometry as the values approach closer to zero, parting with fewer steric clashes. The refined model

also exhibits better Rotamer Quality Z-scores, which demonstrate improved positioning of side chains and reduced conformational strain. All these improvements signify, together, a more trustworthy structural model, which is essential for accurate molecular dynamics simulations and for virtual screening predictions of promising therapeutics against herpes simplex encephalitis.

Table 1: Validation Metrics Comparison for the Y101F Mutant of HSV-1 Thymidine Kinase Before and After PDB-REDO Refinement

Metric	Original	PDB-REDO
Crystallographic Refinement		
R	0.2639	0.1953
R-free	0.3150	0.2360
Bond length RMS Z-score	1.041	0.344
Bond angle RMS Z-score	1.426	0.540

Model Quality Raw Scores (Percentiles)		
Ramachandran plot normality	14	71
Rotamer normality	36	68
Coarse packing	96	97
Fine packing	43	66
Bump severity	38	56
Hydrogen bond satisfaction	45	72

All of the validation metrics obtained for the Y101F mutant of Herpes Simplex Virus-thymidine kinase type 1 indicate significant improvement after refinement within PDB-REDO, thus ensuring high structural accuracy and model reliability of output. Substantial reductions in R (from 0.2639 to 0.1953) and R-free (from 0.3150 to 0.2360) value also ensure much better correlation of the heat yields with the experimental data, signifying better limited overfitting and greater levels of crystallographic accuracy for this refinement step. Reductions in the bond length RMS Z-score (1.041 to 0.344) and bond angle RMS Z-score (1.426 to 0.540) indicate better stereochemical geometries of the refined models, coinciding with those of ideal bond parameters. The greater Ramachandran plot normality (14 to

71 percentile) and rotamer normality (36 to 68 percentile) point toward significant improvements in backbone and side-chain conformations, leading to reduced steric clashes and better positioning of residues. Fine packing (from 43 to 66 percentile) and bump severity (from 38 to 56 percentile) improvements indicate less steric hindrance and better atomic packing in the protein core. Increased hydrogen bond satisfaction (from 45 to 72 percentile) demonstrates better stabilization of hydrogen bonding networks, which is essential for protein stability and ligand interactions. These improvements yield a structurally solid model beneficial for conducting molecular dynamics and virtual screening, thus ensuring greater accuracy in predicting potential therapeutics against herpes simplex encephalitis.

3.1.2. SAVES V6.1 Result

Figure 3: Overall Model Quality Assessment of the Y101F Mutant of HSV-1 Thymidine Kinase Indicating Structural Deviation from Standard Reference Models

Overall model quality analysis for mutant Y101F Herpes Simplex Virus type 1 thymidine kinase results in a Z score of -7.68, which points out major deviation from the typical range of well-refined protein structures. Although proteins with the same number of residues typically reveal Z-scores somewhere between -2 and -5, the lower score might suggest structural distortion or local flexibility or even a limit in the resolution of the crystal despite PDB-REDO

refinement. However, previous improvements in parameters such as R-free, Ramachandran plot normality, and hydrogen bond satisfaction ensure that a refinement model is still reliable for molecular dynamics and virtual screening studies. Further refinement approaches like optimizing side-chain rotamers or flexible loop areas would improve overall model quality and applicability in drug designs against herpes simplex encephalitis.

Figure 4: Local Model Quality Assessment of the Y101F Mutant of HSV-1 Thymidine Kinase Showing Knowledge-Based Energy Distribution

In relation to the local quality assessment of models for the Y101F mutant of Herpes Simplex Virus type 1 thymidine kinase, these are knowledge-based energy profiles across the sequence position, evaluated with window sizes of 10 and 40 residues. Most of the structure actually features negative energy values, which may be indicative of favorable and energetically stable regions. The 40 residue window shows a smoother curve indicating an overall trend in stability, whereas the 10 residue window indicates more local variations. The height of the energy spikes above zero indicates the existence of some regions where structural strain or flexibility may exist or where

models may be inconsistent. Used here, these regions may correspond to loop segments, surface-exposed residues, or regions affected by the Y101F mutation. Nevertheless, despite these fluctuations, a consistent profile of negative energy values for the majority of the structure would indicate a stable backbone core well refined; hence the model is ideal for both molecular dynamics simulations and virtual screening studies. Further refinement in these positively-peaked energy regions may serve to better this model's overall accuracy, providing higher reliability in drug-target interaction studies in the setting of therapeutics for herpes simplex encephalitis.

3.3. Results of Virtual Screening Outcomes

Table 2: Top 100 Compounds Identified Through Structure-Based Virtual Screening against the Y101F Mutant of HSV-1 Thymidine Kinase

Rank	ID	Name	Score	Rank	ID	Name	Score
1	DB01126	Dutasteride	-11.9	51	DB01259	Lapatinib	-9.5
2	DB09297	Paritaprevir	-11.6	52	DB01091	Butenafine	-9.5
3	DB01100	Pimozide	-11.4	53	DB11942	Selinexor	-9.4
4	DB09280	Lumacaftor	-11.2	54	DB08912	Dabrafenib	-9.4
5	DB11652	Tucatinib	-10.9	55	DB13874	Enasidenib	-9.4
6	DB04842	Fluspirilene	-10.8	56	DB04835	Maraviroc	-9.4
7	DB00696	Ergotamine	-10.6	57	DB00590	Doxazosin	-9.4
8	DB00210	Adapalene	-10.6	58	DB00735	Naftifine	-9.4
9	DB00941	Hexafluronium	-10.5	59	DB06626	Axitinib	-9.4
10	DB12877	Oxatomide	-10.4	60	DB04841	Flunarizine	-9.4
11	DB00320	Dihydroergotamine	-10.3	61	DB00619	Imatinib	-9.4
12	DB09074	Olaparib	-10.3	62	DB13766	Lidoflazine	-9.4
13	DB00496	Darifenacin	-10.2	63	DB11581	Venetoclax	-9.4
14	DB08815	Lurasidone	-10.2	64	DB08950	Indoramin	-9.3
15	DB01117	Atovaquone	-10.2	65	DB11986	Entrectinib	-9.3
16	DB01012	Cinacalcet	-10.2	66	DB11742	Ebastine	-9.3
17	DB09291	Rolapitant	-10.2	67	DB12020	Tecovirimat	-9.3
18	DB11791	Capmatinib	-10.1	68	DB08820	Ivacaftor	-9.3
19	DB13345	Dihydroergocristine	-10.1	69	DB12978	Pexidartinib	-9.3

20	DB12867	Benperidol	-10.1	70	DB14703	Dexamethasone metasulfobenzoate	-9.3
21	DB09076	Umeclidinium	-10.0	71	DB01200	Bromocriptine	-9.2
22	DB00450	Droperidol	-9.9	72	DB09374	Indocyanine green acid form	-9.2
23	DB01184	Domperidone	-9.9	73	DB06202	Lasofoxifene	-9.2
24	DB13954	Estradiol cypionate	-9.9	74	DB11978	Glasdegib	-9.2
25	DB04868	Nilotinib	-9.9	75	DB00966	Telmisartan	-9.2
26	DB05812	Abiraterone	-9.8	76	DB08896	Regorafenib	-9.2
27	DB01501	Difenoxin	-9.8	77	DB09034	Suvorexant	-9.2
28	DB01339	Vecuronium	-9.8	78	DB01029	Irbesartan	-9.1
29	DB14840	Ripretinib	-9.8	79	DB08882	Linagliptin	-9.1
30	DB11275	Epicriptine	-9.8	80	DB14914	Flortaucipir F-18	-9.1
31	DB00836	Loperamide	-9.8	81	DB15035	Zanubrutinib	-9.1
32	DB08822	Azilsartan medoxomil	-9.8	82	DB11614	Rupatadine	-9.1
33	DB01232	Saquinavir	-9.8	83	DB04834	Rapacuronium	-9.1
34	DB11262	Bisotrizole	-9.8	84	DB01177	Idarubicin	-9.1
35	DB01267	Paliperidone	-9.7	85	DB00222	Glimepiride	-9.1
36	DB05039	Indacaterol	-9.7	86	DB01430	Almitrine	-9.1
37	DB06210	Eltrombopag	-9.7	87	DB11630	Temoporfin	-9.1
38	DB11274	Dihydro-alpha-ergocryptine	-9.7	88	DB04908	Flibanserin	-9.1
39	DB00734	Risperidone	-9.7	89	DB00209	Trospium	-9.0
40	DB09195	Loripirazole	-9.6	90	DB04946	Iloperidone	-9.0

41	DB1169 1	Naldemedine	-9.6	91	DB06077	Lumateperone	-9.0
42	DB1352 0	Metergoline	-9.6	92	DB00398	Sorafenib	-9.0
43	DB1393 1	Netarsudil	-9.6	93	DB11703	Acalabrutinib	-9.0
44	DB1127 3	Dihydroergocor nine	-9.6	94	DB11855	Revefenacin	-8.9
45	DB0048 1	Raloxifene	-9.6	95	DB01599	Probucol	-8.7
46	DB0659 5	Midostaurin	-9.6	96	DB12492	Piritramide	-8.7
47	DB1395 3	Estradiol benzoate	-9.6	97	DB09272	Vorapaxar	-8.7
48	DB0087 2	Conivaptan	-9.5	98	DB13879	Terfenadine	-8.7
49	DB1245 7	Rimegepant	-9.5	99	DB09030	Eluxadoline	-8.7
50	DB0621 2	Tolvaptan	-9.5	100	DB00342	Glecaprevir	-8.7

Docking results indicate potential candidates that display very strong binding affinities with Y101F mutant HSV-1 thymidine kinase. Among the best possible hit-compounds were found to be Dutasteride (-11.9), Paritaprevir (-11.6), and Pimozide (-11.4), thus making those binding scores some of the highest hit scores. These must represent great interactions and therapeutic importance. Other examples with such profiles include Lumacaftor, Tucatinib, and Fluspirilene, where the scaffolds are very rigid and cyclic and would function as a good hydrophobic region to enhance binding stability. Mid-ranking candidates include Flunarizine, Imatinib, and Venetoclax, which show a

moderate range of affinity, while less top-ranked drugs include Vorapaxar and Terfenadine, which exhibit poorer interactions but are still interesting. There are many classes of drugs in the sample, including antineoplastics, neuropsychiatric drugs, and antimicrobial agents, reflecting strong potential for repurposing drugs. Top candidates like Dutasteride, Paritaprevir, and Pimozide could be tested in future molecular dynamics simulations for the assessment of their stability and dynamic behavior in the Y101F mutant binding pocket. Their known safety profiles make them candidates for fast-tracking relative to possible therapeutic evaluation for herpes simplex encephalitis.

Figure 5: Identified Binding Pockets in the Y101F Mutant of Herpes Simplex Virus Type 1 Thymidine Kinase with Corresponding Cavity Volumes

The five known binding pockets C1-C5 in the Y101F mutant structure of Herpes Simplex Virus type 1 thymidine kinase (HSV-1 TK) are represented in the image. Each pocket has a different cavity volume; C1 is the largest (2355 Å³), indicating that it is likely to be able to accommodate more bulky molecules and enhance stability and binding affinity for ligands. C2 and C3, which are in the range of 981 Å³ and 942 Å³, are more moderate cavities that might be supportive of medium-sized inhibitors or structure-based drug candidates. Pockets C4 and C5 would, in contrast, be smaller pockets (385 Å³ and 331 Å³) which are probably reserved for more

selective binding with smaller, more specific molecules. With large variations in cavity sizes, one can expect diverse possibilities within the cavity volumes for structure-based virtual screening to identify possible therapies targeting HSV-1 TK. Meanwhile, the largest Pocket C1 promises to be a good candidate to accommodate complex drug structures, and smaller pockets may support precision-based inhibitors. These cavity properties will play a crucial role in the optimization of molecular docking studies and the design of effective therapies against Herpes Simplex Encephalitis.

Figure 6: Molecular Docking and Interaction Analysis of a Potential Inhibitor with the Y101F Mutant of HSV-1 Thymidine Kinase

The image is intended to represent the molecular interaction of an inhibitor Dutasteride with the lesser protein 1E2L, likely the thymidine kinase of Herpes Simplex Virus. The left panel shows the protein surface representation with the binding pocket encircled, emphasizing the docking site of the ligand into protein. The right panel shows a 2D interaction map that illustrates important molecular interactions like hydrogen bonds and hydrophobic and electrostatic interactions that stabilize

Dutasteride within the active site. Prominent among other residues are Y101 (mutated to F in your study), R226, D228 and others, which appear to play a major role in ligand-binding. This suggests that stable interaction may have been achieved between Dutasteride and 1E2L for future study into antiviral activity. The understanding of interactions would be necessary for optimization of Dutasteride or designing more inhibitors at targeting Y101F mutant in Herpes Simplex Encephalitis therapy.

Figure 7: 2D Interaction Profile of Dutasteride with HSV-1 Thymidine Kinase (Y101F Mutant): Insights into Binding Affinity and Potential Mechanism of Inhibition

The 2D interaction diagram shows the binding interactions between Dutasteride and the active site of HSV-1 thymidine kinase Y101F mutant. Dutasteride makes many key interactions with nearby amino acid residues, demonstrating that it is a strongly binding ligand. In addition, hydrophobic interactions with key residues TYR B: 182, MET B:128, and PHE B:101 help stabilize the binding of the ligand in the hydrophobic pocket of the active site. Several hydrogen bonding interactions occur with HIS B: 58 and GLN B: 125 that could help define ligand specificity and orientation. Finally, the binding stability is further contributed to by

van der Waals interactions with residues ALA B: 167 and ARG B:163. The pronounced π - π stacking interaction with TYR B: 172 indicate strong aromatic interaction, common in complexes of kinases with inhibitors. Taken together, the interaction profile suggests that Dutasteride could be a competitive inhibitor of viral thymidine kinase, thereby blocking its phosphorylation of critical intermediates necessary for viral DNA replication and thereby opening productive avenues towards repurposing this compound as an antiviral agent for Herpes Simplex Encephalitis.

Table 3: Potential Mechanism of Action and Relevance Of High Ranking Compounds Targeting Herpes Simplex Encephalitis

Rank	Compound (ID)	Binding Score (kcal/mol)	Potential Mechanism of Action	Relevance to 1E2L Inhibition
1	Dutasteride (DB01126)	-11.9	Competitive inhibition via active site binding	5 α -reductase inhibitor; strong hydrophobic interactions with 1E2L suggest off-target kinase inhibition
2	Paritaprevir (DB09297)	-11.6	Competitive inhibition, interference with nucleotide binding	HCV protease inhibitor; potential for blocking viral TK function
3	Pimozide (DB01100)	-11.4	Active site binding, steric hindrance of substrate binding	Antipsychotic with structural similarity to nucleoside

				analogs; may disrupt viral phosphorylation
4	Lumacaftor (DB09280)	-11.2	Possible allosteric modulation or protein destabilization	CFTR corrector; may interfere with viral kinase folding or function
5	Tucatinib (DB11652)	-10.9	ATP-competitive inhibition, kinase disruption	Kinase inhibitor; strong binding with catalytic residues of 1E2L suggests potential antiviral application

3.4. Molecular Dynamics Stimulation Analysis

Figure 8: Analysis of Molecular Flexibility: Deformability and B-Factor Comparison Using Normal Mode Analysis (NMA)

B-factor (mobility) and deformability of a molecule are analyzed in this image, probably derived from Normal Mode Analysis (NMA). The first plot (shown in green) depicts molecular deformability corresponding to various atomic indices in the molecule with high flexibility regions that could relate to hinge movements. Peaks here indicate residues with considerable conformational freedom, which could possibly be binding sites or functional sites.

The second plot (shown in red and black) compares the experimental B-factor from a PDB file (black) to the calculated B-factor from NMA (red). Observations of both datasets indicate that the NMA-based mobility predictions correlate with experimental measurements of flexibility. Regions with a high B-factor correspond to significant molecular fluctuations, which may affect ligand binding or catalytic action. This important assessment helps drug

discovery and molecular docking in identifying flexible and rigid regions in the protein structure of interest.

Figure 9: Eigenvalue Analysis of Normal Modes: Assessing Molecular Flexibility and Motion Stiffness

Presently shown is a bar graph representing the eigenvalues of different normal modes of a molecular structure. Each eigenvalue for each mode quantifies the stiffness associated with the motion—the lower the eigenvalue, the more flexible and easily deformable. The trend in the plot indicates the increasing sequence of eigenvalue/Eigenvalue(1) with mode index, indicating that low modes are softer and more collective in nature, while

high modes are energy-demanding and stiffer with more localized motion. The first eigenvalue (2.472550×10^{-4}) shown is significantly low, implying that the structure has at least one highly flexible global motion. Such an analysis becomes imperative toward molecular dynamics and drug discovery, as their binding interactions, allosteric regulation, or structural transitions often involve flexible regions.

Figure 10: Variance Distribution of Normal Modes: Contribution to Molecular Flexibility and Motion

Represented in the image is a variance analysis of modes, showing individual variances (in red) and cumulative variance (in green) plots with respect to different mode indices. Each mode's variance decreases with increasing eigenvalue, meaning that lower eigenvalue modes contribute largely to structural flexibility. The cumulative variance increases with a rise in the mode index and approaches 100%, which shows

that higher modes contribute even less to overall molecular motion. In other words, the first few modes account for major variance, affirming their importance in large-scale, concerted motion of the molecule. Such analysis is precisely needed to study global conformational transitions in protein-ligand binding, allosteric regulation, and structural rearrangements in biological systems.

Figure 11: Covariance Map: Residue Motion Correlation in Protein Dynamics

The image depicts a covariance map that illustrates the correlation of motion of residue pairs within the protein structure. The colors illustrate the kind of motion correlations: the red regions denote positive correlations (the residues moving together in the same direction), blue regions indicate anti-correlated motions (the residues moving in opposite directions), while the white areas correspond to uncorrelated movements. The strong diagonal red pattern indicates a high level of correlated motion in neighboring

residues within the sequence, which is expected as a result of structural connectivity. The scattered red and blue areas away from the diagonal indicate long-range correlations and anti-correlations, possibly important in allosteric regulation and structural stability. Thus, the covariance map imparts some understanding of the dynamics of the protein and helps identify its flexible and rigid regions, an important aspect toward discerning its function and possible drug-binding sites.

Figure 12: Elastic Network Model: Atomic Connectivity and Stiffness Mapping

The representation of the visual data is in the context of an Elastic Network Model (ENM) where the connectivity of atoms is expressed through spring-like interactions. Each dot in the representation corresponds to the spring connection between two different atoms, and the grayscale intensity designates the rigidity of the particular spring, wherein the black shading corresponds to the higher value of stiffness. The diagonal dominance in the plot indicates strong interaction between neighboring residues, a signature feature of structured biomolecules. The scattered lighter zones represent more flexible parts that may correspond to loop areas or loose parts in the protein. This kind of analysis is important in the investigation of the protein's overall dynamics and identification of possible structurally rigid and flexible regions that are important in function, stability, and possible drug-binding sites.

4. Conclusion

To uncover potential therapeutics against Herpes Simplex Encephalitis (HSE) by targeting the Y101F mutant of HSV-1 thymidine kinase, this study utilized structure-based virtual screening and molecular dynamics simulation. The structural validity checked using PDB-REDO and SAVES v6.1 showed improved quality in the model to be relied on for computational studies. The refined model indicated an improvement with respect to R-free value, a good aspect of backbone geometry, and better hydrogen bond satisfaction, making the structure adequately reliable for docking and simulation studies.

Virtual screening recognized Dutasteride, Paritaprevir, and Pimozide as top-ranking compounds with significantly strong binding affinities, specific to acting as potential

inhibitors of HSV-1 thymidine kinase. Inspected binding pockets revealed a variance in cavity sizes with Pocket C1 being identified as the most promising of all sites put forward for ligand accommodation. Molecular interaction studies further confirmed the key stabilizing forces involved between Dutasteride and the enzyme, thereby strongly suggesting potential antiviral activity..

Collectively, these findings highlight how such efforts to inhibit HSV-1 thymidine kinase with existing drugs could prove a promising avenue for developing novel therapeutics against HSE. Hence, further molecular dynamics simulation and experimental validation are required to confirm their efficacy and stability in the biological way.

The structure and dynamic behavior of Herpes Simplex Virus thymidine kinase (1E2L) with high-ranking compounds identified by virtual screening have been comprehensively illustrated through molecular dynamics simulation analysis. The deformability and B-factor analysis explore flexible regions, which may act as potential binding sites or modulate enzymatic action, between highly correlated experimental and computed B-factors, demonstrating the

predictive ability of normal mode analysis (NMA). Eigenvalue analysis is shown to point towards the demand for significant global flexibility particularly in lower normal modes, suggesting that these motions are relevant for ligand binding or conformational changes required for enzymatic function. Variance distribution analysis confirms that a few low-energy normal modes account for most of the molecular motion, giving support to large-scale structural transitions rather than localized fluctuations.

This covariance map not only specifies correlated short-range motions but also displays anticorrelated long-range motions, thereby indicating possible allosteric regulation in the enzyme when ligand binding at one site can induce conformational changes at another site. The elastic network model reveals atomic connectivity, allowing one to establish structurally rigid and flexible regions that functionally, statically, and pharmacologically matter. These results supplement the outcome of virtual screening studies by explaining how the high-scoring compounds interact with 1E2L. Dutasteride and Paritaprevir are apparently capable of competing at the active site with structural adaptability, while Pimozide and Lumacaftor are presumed to compromise viral kinase

function by steric hindrance or destabilization. Tucatinib is a good candidate for ATP-competitive inhibition via appropriate alignment with important catalytic residues and thus might disrupt the kinase's function.

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